

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Dy(III) with *o*-Hydroxyacetophenoneoxime and its Substituted Derivatives

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The stability constants of Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Dy(III) complexes of some substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oximes have been determined potentiometrically in water-dioxane 25%–75% v/v at $\mu \sim 0.1$ M NaClO₄ and $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The validity of the linear relation $\log K = apk + b$ and the Born relation $E = e^2/2r(1-1/D)$ was examined for the rare earth complexes.

VERY few metal complexes of chelating agents having –OH and =N–OH as electron donor groups appear to have been systematically investigated. Some workers^{1,2} used *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime and resacetophenone oxime as analytical and colorimetric reagents for complex formation. The present work deals with a systematic study of stability constants of some substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oximes with a few rare earth ions. The metal-ligand stability constants were determined by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

Materials: The details regarding the preparation of ligands and the experimental technique employed for the Bjerrum-Calvin titration are given in an earlier communication⁴.

Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Dy(III) were used in the form of their nitrates (AnalaR grade) obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. The solutions were prepared in perchloric acid solution of suitable normality.

The Bjerrum-Calvin titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations if (i) free HClO₄ ($8.52 \times 10^{-3} M$), (ii) free HClO₄ ($8.52 \times 10^{-3} M$) + reagent ($1.990 \times 10^{-3} M$), (iii) free HClO₄ ($8.52 \times 10^{-3} M$) + reagent ($1.99 \times 10^{-3} M$) + rare earth ion ($2.50 \times 10^{-4} M$) and (iv) free HClO₄ + rare earth ion ($2.500 \times 10^{-4} M$) against standard sodium hydroxide solution ($2.88 \times 10^{-1} M$) added from the burette. The ionic strength of the solution was maintained constant at 0.1M by addition of sodium perchlorate solution.

pH meter: Leeds-Northrup A.C. operated pH indicator in combination with Leeds-Northrup, std., 1190-30 (one black dot) glass electrode and std. 1199-31 saturated calomel electrode was used for pH measurement.

Results and Calculations

For the calculation of stability constants of rare earth complexes it was assumed that factors like

hydrolysis of rare earth ions and presence of polynuclear hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing complexes were absent. The assumptions were justified on the following grounds.

(i) The pH meter reading 'B' for hydrolysis of all the rare earth ions under investigation was around 6.5. The deviation of metal-complex titration curve from the reagent curve was noticed around pH meter reading B = 4.5.

(ii) The solutions employed being very dilute, the probability of existence of polynuclear species under experimental conditions was not expected to be high.

Values of \bar{n} (metal-ligand formation number) were calculated using Irving-Rossotti expression. The highest values of \bar{n} in the region B = 6.5 was 1.7 which indicates the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The formation of the 1:2 complex lies in the region of hydrolysis and hence its existence is uncertain. The difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was less than 1. $\log K_1 K_2$ was obtained by the method of least squares and $\log K_1$ was calculated by pointwise calculations. $\log K_2$ (tentative value was obtained as difference (Table 1). The observed pH meter readings 'B' were used for the calculation of stability constants.

Discussion

The rare earth metal ions differ from each other in the number of electrons in the 4f orbitals which are effectively shielded from interaction with ligand orbitals by electrons in the 5s and 5p orbitals. Hybridization would involve normally unoccupied higher energy orbitals (e.g., 5d, 6s, 6p) and this may be expected to occur with the most strongly coordinating ligands. Rare earths, therefore, normally form ionic compounds. The possibility of covalent interaction, however, cannot be completely excluded as reported in the case of acetylacetonate chelates of rare earths⁵.

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TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Temperature—30°

Ligand No.	Name of the ligand	*Proton stability constants $\log PKH_2$	Ce(III)			Pr(III)			Nd(III)			Dy(III)		
			$\log K_1K_2$ (Method of least-squares)	$\log K_1$ (Point-wise calculations)	$\log K_2$ (By difference)	$\log K_1K_2$ (Method of least-squares)	$\log K_1$ (Point-wise calculations)	$\log K_2$ (By difference)	$\log K_1K_2$ (Method of least-squares)	$\log K_1$ (Point-wise calculations)	$\log K_2$ (By difference)	$\log K_1K_2$ (Method of least-squares)	$\log K_1$ (Point-wise calculations)	$\log K_2$ (By difference)
1.	OHAP0**	11.86	17.86	9.21	8.65	17.89	9.27	8.62	17.73	9.16	8.57	18.27	9.40	8.87
2.	RAPO	11.14	15.91	8.16	7.75	16.03	8.22	7.81	16.87	9.04	7.83	18.44	10.11	8.33
3.	5-methyl-OHAP0	12.11	18.45	9.59	8.86	18.34	9.55	8.79	18.20	9.31	8.89	18.95	9.73	9.22
4.	3-methyl-OHAP0	12.05	19.03	10.11	8.92	17.51	9.13	9.38	17.68	9.24	8.44	19.34	10.04	9.30
5.	5-chloro-OHAP0	11.28	16.72	8.67	8.05	16.84	8.61	8.23	16.90	8.68	8.22	17.42	9.02	8.40
6.	5-bromo-OHAP0	11.27	16.87	8.92	7.95	16.29	8.49	7.80	16.20	8.34	7.86	17.24	8.96	8.28
7.	3-chloro-OHAP0	10.77	15.88	8.32	7.56	15.72	8.20	7.52	15.36	8.04	7.32	16.44	8.52	7.92
8.	3-bromo-OHAP0	11.04	15.91	8.33	7.58	15.58	8.09	7.49	16.21	8.60	7.61	16.76	8.75	8.01
9.	5-iodo-OHAP0	11.16	16.96	8.97	7.99	16.12	8.29	7.83	15.85	8.18	7.67	16.66	8.45	8.21
10.	5-nitro-OHAP0	8.97	12.27	6.63	5.64	11.92	6.32	5.60	11.45	6.14	5.31	12.34	6.61	5.73

* The $\log PKH_2$ values have been taken from Ph.D. thesis submitted to the Marathwada University by D. B. Ingle.

** Ortho—Hydroxyacetophenoneoxime.

If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E = e^2/2r$. $(1-1/D)$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge 'e' and radius 'r' in a medium of dielectric constant 'D'. Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the log K values should increase linearly with e^2/r .

The plots of e^2/r versus $\log K_1$ values of the rare earth complexes (Fig. 1) do not exhibit any linear increase of $\log K_1$ with increase in e^2/r . The probable explanation of nonlinearity could be that the

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log K_1$ vs e^2/r for Rare earth complexes of OHAPOs :

assumption about ionic character of metal-ligand bond on which the linear relation is based is not valid. The other probable causes are (i) coordination number of metal ion greater than six, and (ii) steric factor.

Validity of $\log K = apk + b$ relation : The linear relation between $\log K_1$ and $\log {}^P K_2^H$ (pk) did not show strict validity for 1 : 1 complexes of the rare earth ions (Fig. 2). The values of slope of the straight lines passing through a majority of points are given below :

Metal	Slope
Ce(III)	0.85
Pr(III)	1.00
Nd(III)	0.90
Dy(III)	0.83

The magnitude of the slope of such correlation plots depends on a number of factors such as ionisation potential of the metal ion, nuclear repulsion between metal ion and donor atoms, tendency of metal ion to form π bonds and ligand field stabilization. According to Ernst and Menashi⁶, for transition metal complexes, the effect of substitution in the ligand on the stability of metal-ligand complexes as compared to that of proton-ligand complexes will be

- i) to the same extent if slope = 1
- ii) to a lesser extent if slope < 1
- iii) to a greater extent if slope > 1

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log K_1$ vs. $\log K_2$ for Rare earth complexes of OHAPOs :

Cerous—O
Praseodymium—X
Dysprosium—□
Neodymium—△

This observation has been examined in the case of some transition metal complexes⁶⁻⁹ but not for rare earth complexes. If the observation of Ernst and Menashi is applied to rare earth complexes studied by the authors, it would mean that the stability of the rare earth complexes is lower than that of the proton-ligand complexes.

Jones⁷ suggested on the basis of purely electrostatic model that the slope should increase with the increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation (equal to the radius of the cation plus a constant). It is seen that the slope values for rare earth complexes are higher than those for transition metal complexes. This observation is in agreement with Jones' suggestion.

References

- S. N. PODDAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 537; *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1963, 28, 586.
- K. S. BHATKI, A. T. RANE and M. B. KABADI, *Proc. Sym. Chem. Coord. Comp.*, Agra (India), 1959; 1960, Part III, 78.
- K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *Current Sci.*, 1958, 27, 337.
- H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
- D. B. INGLE and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, (Communicated).
- T. D. MOELLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
- Z. L. ERNST and J. MENASHI, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 591, 2838.
- J. G. JONES, J. C. TOMKINSON, J. B. POOLS and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2001.
- R. M. TICHANE and W. E. BENNETT; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1293.
- A. T. ATHWALE, L. H. PRABHU and D. G. VARTAK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, 28, 1237.